

THE IMPACT OF USING FINE RECYCLED CONCRETE AGGREGATES ON RHEOLOGICAL AND HARDENED MORTAR CHARACTERISTICS

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ABSTRACT: *The growing demand for materials for concrete production is depleting natural reserves of aggregates, making the development of sustainable alternatives urgent. This study aims to examine the mechanicals and rheologicals performances of a mortar containing recycled sand from old demolition concrete. Different substitution rates by volume (0%, 25%, 50%, 75% and 100%) for the recycled sand were the focus of the experimental study. Spread, shear stress and plastic viscosity tests were conducted on the fresh mortar. Compressive and flexural strength tests are carried out to evaluate the mechanical performances of the recycled mortar, as well as the impact of the application of these aggregates on durability, including sorptivity and shrinkage. The results indicate that recycled sand can be substituted for natural sand, even though it is detrimental to the durability of the mortar. Predictive models were developed to relate test parameters to mechanical strength, rheological behavior, and durability.*

KEYWORDS: *Recycled fine aggregates, Superplasticizer, Rheological properties, Mechanical resistance, durability.*

1 INTRODUCTION

The integration of recycled aggregates in the construction sector represents a promising innovation, reducing dependence on natural aggregates. However, their high water absorption capacity and limited mechanical performance can affect the properties of concrete and mortars in their fresh and hardened states.

Existing research on recycled concrete aggregates (RCA) converges on a common observation: their heterogeneous composition leads to significant variations compared to natural aggregates. The characteristics concerned include irregular morphology, marked angularity, rough surface, reduced density and increased porosity. In addition, their high humidity content, high water absorption and limited mechanical performance constitute major challenges for their integration into cement matrices (Zhang et al., 2025; Singh & Kapoor 2024; Cabral et al., 2010).

The physical properties of FRCA play a crucial role in mortar mix design and influence fresh mortar properties such as spreading and setting time. Research studies have shown a wide range of water absorption values in the case of FRCA, the maximum water absorption recorded was 13.48% (Poon et al., 2009) and the minimum was 5.25% (Salahuddin et al., 2020). For a given granular fraction, FRCA would absorb more water than natural fine aggregates. This is due to the presence of adherent mortar, which generates increasingly long capillaries, thus increasing water absorption (Djerbi Tegger, 2012).

The impact of FRCA substitution on the bulk density of fresh mortar is studied by several researchers, where in the study conducted by (Garg & Shrivastava, 2023), demonstrates that the bulk density decreases as the percentage of replacement increases.

Most researchers have shown a reduction in the spread of mortars with the increase in the percentages of recycled concrete sand in the mortar mixtures. The

study by (Khelafi et al., 2023), noted that the spread observed for all mortars based on recycled sand is 5% less compared to those of the reference mortar. (Khatib, 2005) and (Yacoub et al., 2019) pointed out that the difference in the spread values was mainly due to the water absorption rate of recycled aggregates, which varied between 5% and 10%. According to (Gomart et al., 2013), when recycled sand replaces more than 75% of the original sand, it becomes difficult, if not impossible, to control the typical spread of mortars.

The mortar's rheological properties are impacted by the complex physical characteristics of FRCA. Studies have shown that FRCA mortar exhibits significantly higher yield stress and plastic viscosity compared to conventional mortar (Ma et al., 2024). According to (Ma et al., 2024), this difference can be attributed to the angular and irregular shape of FRCA particles, unlike the smoother surfaces of natural sand (NS). The apparent viscosity of mortar exhibits minor fluctuations during mixing due to collisions between rotating mixer blades and aggregates, yet overall maintains stable values. In contrast, the angular morphology and rough surface texture of FRCA particles generate significantly higher interparticle friction compared to conventional aggregates. Furthermore, more cement slurry is needed in the cement-based packing system with FRCA in order to fill the gaps between the aggregate particles. This phenomenon consequently decreases the required volume of cement paste necessary to achieve target rheological characteristics, which leads to a decline in the recycled mortar's rheological qualities as replacement increases.

The factors that can influence the compressive strength of concretes and mortars based on recycled concrete sand are mainly the w/c ratio, origin of natural aggregates, the interaction of fine and coarse elements, and the quantity of mortar attached to the natural aggregates of the FRCA. Experimental results by (Kou et al., 2008) demonstrated a progressive enhancement in mortar resistance at substitution levels of 25%, 50%, and 75% while maintaining a constant spread compared to the reference mortar. However, at 100% replacement the resistance is equal to that of the reference mortar. (Evangelista & de Brito, 2007) showed that the compressive strength varies very little when the substitution rate remains below 50%, but at 100% replacement, a decrease in resistance is observed. The experimental findings of (Sosa et al., 2023) demonstrate a significant improvement in compressive strength with higher FRCA incorporation. This enhancement is attributed to the reduced effective water-to-cement (w/c) ratio resulting from the dried FRCA's water absorption,

which effectively offsets the negative impact of FRCA porosity. To address the absorbed mixing water, literature proposes various compensation methods. A balanced approach involves using dried FRCA with a slight increase in mixing water relative to the control mortar. However, this increase must not match the FRCA's full water absorption capacity or require the addition of superplasticizer to maintain the same workability. (Ait Mohamed Amer et al., 2016; Ait Mohamed Amer et al., 2021; Salhi et al., 2024).

The tensile strength of mortars is another important property for evaluating the quality of mortars. In most research studies it remains closely linked to compressive strength. Experimental results reported by (Fang et al., 2022) revealed that mortar mixtures containing recycled aggregates exhibited measurable improvements in flexural strength compared to conventional formulations.

Drying shrinkage represents a critical durability parameter for maintenance mortars. (Jesus et al., 2019) demonstrated that mortars incorporating fine recycled concrete aggregate (FRCA) exhibit significantly higher shrinkage compared to conventional mortars. This behavior may be attributed to an increased cement content required in FRCA-modified mixes, and elevated capillary pore stresses induced by the aggregate's porous microstructure. Further investigation by (Li et al., 2020) revealed that the initial saturation degree of FRCA substantially influences shrinkage behavior, with pre-saturated aggregates exacerbating drying shrinkage across all replacement ratios.

Capillary absorption (sorptivity) serves as a key durability indicator, quantifying a mortar's capacity for water uptake through capillary action (Safer et al., 2024). Research by Saba and Assaad (2021) revealed that while low FRCA replacement rates ($\leq 30\%$) show negligible impact on sorptivity, higher substitution levels ($> 50\%$) lead to significant increases in water absorption. This behavior stems primarily from FRCA's intrinsic porosity, which enhances water permeability (Neno et al., 2014). Multiple factors govern this capillary absorption process, including the composition and fines content of recycled aggregates, and the pore structure disparity between new cement paste and recycled aggregates containing residual mortar (Katz & Kulisch, 2017). (Kumar, 2019) further demonstrated that the attached mortar present on FRCA surfaces acts as preferential pathways for water absorption, with this effect becoming progressively more pronounced at higher FRCA contents.

This study investigates the utilization of aggregates derived from crushed recycled concrete

blocks as partial replacements for natural sand in new mortar production. Fine recycled concrete aggregates (FRCA) were incorporated in a dried state to evaluate their water absorption effects and determine the optimal methodology for enhancing performance. The rheological, mechanical, and durability properties of FRCA-modified mortars were systematically quantified and benchmarked against conventional mortars containing ordinary aggregates. This approach is part of a circular economy perspective, aiming to reduce the extraction of natural resources while recovering construction waste.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

2.1 Materials

Blended cement (CEM II) containing 10% of limestone powder was used for all mixtures at specific surface area of 320 m²/kg. Its chemical composition and physical properties are given in Table 1. Natural river sand (NS) served as the reference aggregate, while FRCA was laboratory-produced by crushing 1-year-old concrete blocks. The crushed material was sieved (≤ 4 mm) and incorporated as NS replacement by volume. The granulometric curves of cement, NS and FRCA are presented in Fig. 1. The physico-mechanical characteristics of the used aggregates are summarized in Table 2. To maintain consistent workability across all mixtures, a polycarboxylate-ether-based superplasticizer was incorporated. This admixture served to enhancing the fresh mortar's flow characteristics and compensating for water absorption by FRCA particles, thereby ensuring uniform fluidity in all formulations.

Fig. 1 Particle size distributions of the two sands and cement.

Table 1: Mineral and chemical components of the utilized cement.

Chemical composition (%)							
CaO	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	SO ₃	K ₂ O	PAF
62,17	22,6	4,20	3,55	0,63	2,19	0,42	1,84
Mineralogical composition (%)							
C3S		C2S		C3A		C4AF	
41,8		33,3		5,1		10,7	

Table 2: Physico-mechanical characteristics of the aggregates used

	NS	FRCA
Fineness module	1.71	2.79
Sand equivalent	79.00	81.00
Bulk density (kg/m ³)	1561.8	1487.2
Specific density (Kg/m ³)	2650.2	2520.8
Los Angeles (%)	-	-
Water absorption (%)	0.82	9.39

2.2 Mortar composition

The proportions of the various components of the mortar were determined by providing maximum compactness of mortar products. A control mixture (0% FRCA) was prepared using 100% natural sand (NS). While experimental mixtures incorporated FRCA as partial NS replacement at volumetric substitution rates of 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100%. All the mortars were made with three w/c ratios (0.4, 0.5 and 0.6). The same fluidity of 80% for the different mortars was kept by incorporating the required amount of superplasticizer. The different composition of the sample mortars and the mixing protocols are shown in Table 3 and Table 4 respectively.

Table 3: Mortar Compositions and Nomenclature

	Materials			SP (%)		
	Cement (g)	NS (g)	FRCA (g)	w/c = 0,6	w/c = 0,5	w/c = 0,4
0% FRCA	450	1350	0,00	0,2	0,6	1,4
25% FRCA	450	1012,5	320,94	0,4	0,9	2
50% FRCA	450	675	641,89	0,6	1,3	2,8
75% FRCA	450	337,5	962,83	1	2,2	*
100% FRCA	450	0	1283,77	1,6	2,8	*

(*The test cannot be performed)

2.3 Tests procedures

After mixing the different mortars, the fluidity was first checked by the spreading test carried out using a flow table test. The conduct of this test was carried out according to the (ASTM C 230, 2008) standard. The prepared mortar is placed in a truncated mold for the test, and once it has been unmolded on a shaking table, it is shot 15 times in 15 seconds. The diameter of the mortar that is produced is then measured. The increase in mortar diameter over the original diameter is known as the spread in percentage.

Following the measurement of the spread, the mortars were transferred to the rheometer device shown in fig. 2. An agitator with electronic speed control and torque recording, a vane that is 10 cm high and 5 cm in diameter, and a container that is 13 cm high and 10 cm in diameter make up this rheometer's three main components. Every mortar was examined using the method outlined below (Hamza et al., 2014):

The process begins by pouring the prepared mortar into a securely fixed container to prevent movement. Next, the vane is centered and immersed in the mortar, ensuring its upper part aligns with the mortar surface. The friction total torque (M) is then measured at different speed levels (Ω) using a rheometer, yielding a linear relationship :

$$M = M_0 + k\Omega \quad (1)$$

Where M_0 is the initial torque and k is a proportionality constant. Finally, the rheological parameters, yield stress (τ) and plastic viscosity (μ), are determined by analyzing the shear stress (τ_0) versus shear rate ($\dot{\gamma}$) curve using the Bingham model:

$$\tau = \tau_0 + \mu \dot{\gamma} \quad (2)$$

Where τ represents shear stress at a given shear rate. This regression-based approach allows for the characterization of the mortar's flow behavior.

Fig. 2 Principal components of the rheometer test.

Specimens were taken out of their molds after a day and kept in humid rooms with a steady temperature of 20°C.

Prismatic mortar specimens measuring 40 x 40 x 160 mm³ were used to test the tensile strength by bending for each variable. The mortars' compressive strength was assessed using the half-prisms that were acquired from the bending test, which is conducted using a three-point bending press. Mechanical strengths were assessed at three, seven, twenty-eight, and ninety days of age.

To measure the drying shrinkage, 40x40x160 mm³ prismatic test pieces were used, covered at both ends with a waterproof layer to prevent desiccation and prevent edge effect during measurements. The specimens are unmolded the first day after casting and stored under ambient laboratory conditions. When measuring shrinkage, the test pieces are placed in a shrinkage deformation measurement frame equipped with a comparator with an accuracy of 1µm.

The capillary water absorption test makes it possible to characterize the water transfer capacity of a mortar to absorb and transmit water by capillary action. In this study, the test is carried out on prismatic samples of 40x40x160 mm³ according to standard (EN 1015-18, 2003), previously dried in the oven at approximately 80°C until constant weight. They are then placed in a tray so that their lower surface up to 5 mm is in contact with water. Lateral sealing is ensured using adhesive tape to achieve unidirectional flow. The weight of the samples is measured at different times: 0 min, 15min, 30min, 1h, 2h, 4h, 6h, 8h and 24h. The only precaution to take is to remove the film of water retained on the underside of the sample before each weighing using absorbent paper. The tests are carried out under laboratory conditions ($T = 20 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and relative humidity $\text{RH} = 45 \pm 10\%$). The water absorption test by capillary action was carried out after 28 days of curing.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Impact of FRCA on the spread of mortar without superplasticization

Recycled aggregates have the characteristic of high absorption capacity. This property remains true regardless of the origin of the parent concrete as shown in the literature. A clear reduction in mortar spreading has been observed when SBRs are used. For a W/C ratio of 0.4, 0.5 and 0.6, fig. 3 show the results of the spreading of non-superplasticized mortars for the different FRCA substitution rates. When the FRCA are used at the dried state before

mixing, the spreading shows a monotonic decrease with the rate of substitution of NS by FRCA.

By increasing the percentage of SBR in the mortar, the spreading marks a reduction of 62% and 90% for the w/c ratios of 0.6 and 0.5 respectively for an ordinary mortar to a mortar made only with FRCA. This can be attributed to the rough surface texture, angularity in FRCA as reported by (Khatib, 2005) and (Yacoub et al., 2019), where they pointed out that the difference in the spreading values of mortars was mainly due to the water absorption rate of the recycled aggregates, which varied between 5% and 10%.

According to (Gomart et al., 2013), when recycled sand replaces more than 75% of the original sand, it becomes difficult, if not impossible, to handle the regular spreading of mortars.

Fig. 3 Variation of flow mortar (spread %) according to the substitution rate of NS by FRCA.

3.2 Superplasticizer requirement

In order to keep the same spread for all the mixtures of mortars used, a quantity of superplasticizer was added, Fig. 4 shows the needed superplasticizer for a plastic spread of 80%. Where, when incorporating FRCA into mortar mixtures a clear increase in the needed superplasticizer was observed, this increase is more significant by reducing the w/c ratio; where for mixtures of 50% substitution of FRCA an increase in the quantity of superplasticizer of 0.4%, 0.7% and 1.4%, compared to the control mortars, for w/c ratios 0.6; 0.5 and 0.4 respectively. It was also noted that beyond 50% substitution for w/c ratios 0.5 and 0.6 the increase in the demand for superplasticizer is greater, moreover quantities of superplasticizer of 1% and 1.5% have been added to mixtures of w/c ratio of 0.5 and 0.6 respectively between the substitution percentages of 50% to 100%, but these quantities were only of values of 0.4% and 0.7% between the substitution percentages of 0% to 50%. For mixtures with a w/c ratio of 0.4% and for percentages of substitutions which exceed 50%, the dosage of superplasticizer is

exceeded to achieve the same spread, therefore the tests for this substitution rate could not be carried out.

Fig. 4 The needed Superplasticizer for the various mortars studied.

3.3 Rheological properties

To assess rheological properties including yield stress and plastic viscosity, mortars with an 80% spread were chosen for each mortar mix and w/c ratio. It is evident from the results in Figs 5 and 6 that when the w/c ratio or FRCA ratio rises, so do the yield stress and plastic viscosity values. For a w/c ratio of 0.6 and 0.5, respectively, an increase in substitution rate from 0% to 100% results in yield stresses of 20.16 and 18.42% as well as increases in plastic viscosity of 24.79 and 17.87%. With a w/c ratio of 0.4, the yield stress increased by 11.11% and the plastic viscosity by 27.36% from 0 to 50% substitution rate.

This decrease in rheological parameters can be explained by the irregular shape and multiple edges of the RFA increase the relative friction between the aggregates which leads to an increase in the rheological parameters (Ma et al., 2024). The latter authors explained that this phenomenon during the mortar mixing process, the collision between the rotary and the aggregate causes some fluctuations in the apparent viscosity, but it basically remains at the same level, moreover, in the packing system at cement base containing FRCA, more cement slurry is required to fill the spaces between the aggregate particles, thus ultimately decreasing the amount of cement slurry to provide its rheological properties.

From the received effects, it will be shown the critical effect of the substitution price of NS through FRCA, dosage of SP and w/c ratio at the rheological parameters of mortar. So it becomes more interesting to find a courting that hyperlinks every rheological parameter with the mortar composition. On the basis of a couple of correlations, two relationships are observed that explicit the variation of the rheological parameter in step with the mortar composition:

Yield stress:

$$\tau_0 = 160 (1 + 0.69 R_A) \left(1 - 0.122 S_p - 1.2 \frac{w}{c} \right) \quad (3)$$

Plastic viscosity:

$$\mu = 55 (1 + 0.496 R_A) \left(1 - 0.075 S_p - 1.259 \frac{w}{c} \right) \quad (4)$$

In which τ_0 and μ represents yield stress and plastic viscosity of mortars, R_A is the substitution ratio of SN by FRCA, w/c is the water to cement ratio and S_p represents the dosage of superplasticizer.

The experimental values of rheological parameters and the estimated rheological parameters using equations (3) and (4) are compared in Figs 7 and 8, respectively. The correlation coefficients are really close to the unit, and the linear relationship seems convincing. For the yield stress and plastic viscosity, they use values of 0.9223 and 0.9437, respectively. The useful impact of SP, FRCA, and w/c ratio in lowering the mortar's rheological characteristics is clearly shown by the study of the observed patterns. While the trade of FRCA ratio and SP dose effects the yield strain fee more than plastic viscosity, it appears that the trade inside the w/c ratio maintains an equal impact on both parameters in both expressions.

Fig. 5 Effect of FRCA substitution on the yield stress of mortar.

Fig. 6 Effect of FRCA substitution on the plastic viscosity of mortar.

Fig. 7 Correlation between theoretical and experimental yield stress values of mortars with different mix compositions.

Fig. 8 correlation between mortars' measured and calculated plastic viscosities using different tested mixes.

3.4 Compressive strength

Figs 9, 10, and 11 illustrate how the compressive strength of mortar containing FRCA changes over time in a manner similar to that of regular mortar. The results for compressive strength show that recycled aggregates have a beneficial effect. The w/c ratio and, more specifically, the amount of superplasticizer used to accomplish the same spreading are directly related to this impact. When superplasticizer is used, the spreading is increased for the same w/c ratio, and if the spreading is maintained at the same level, the compressive strength is increased by decreasing the w/c ratio.

The replacement of NS by FRCA causes a change in compressive strength. For a curing age of 90 days and for a w/c ratio of 0.5 and a substitution rate of 100% of NS by FRCA, the compressive strength increases by approximately 17.9 MPa. On the other hand, for a w/c ratio of 0.6, this increase is only 8.2 MPa for the same substitution rate. It can be concluded that the use of FRCA requires an adequate dosage of superplasticizer in accordance with an adequate range of w/c ratio. This increase in compressive strength is due to the rougher surface texture of FRCA than that of ordinary aggregates, this causes an increase in friction between the paste and the aggregate surface which creates a solid transition zone and improves mechanical strength

strength (Jesus et al., 2019). (Kou et al., 2008) concluded that absorbed water driven by FRCA may contribute to the formation and growth of additional HSCs in hair pores. Its refinement, its filler effect, and its transformation of coarse capillary pores into smaller ones can lead to the improvement in the compressive strength observed.

Fig. 9 Effect of FRCA substitution rate on compressive strength development (w/c=0.6).

Fig. 10 Effect of FRCA substitution rate on compressive strength development (w/c=0.5).

Fig. 11 Effect of FRCA substitution rate on compressive strength development (w/c=0.4).

3.5 Flexural strength

The flexural strengths obtained confirm those of compression and demonstrate a positive effect of recycled aggregates. In most cases, a correlation can

be observed between the flexural strength of mortar and its compressive strength. From this, it can be inferred that the flexural strength also improves as the compressive strength increases. Figs. 12, 13 and 14 shows the effect of FRCA on the flexural strength at several curing ages of mortars, for w/c ratio of 0.6, 0.5 and 0.4, respectively. Flexural strength follows a similar trend to the compressive strength of mortars, it can see from the collected data that the increase in strength is comparable to that previously reported for their compressive strength.

The flexural strength exhibits a notable increase with higher FRCA content, primarily attributed to the reduced effective w/c ratio resulting from FRCA's water absorption. In this case, the negative influence of FRCA porosity is outweighed by this beneficial effect. However, existing literature proposes diverse methods for adjusting mix water, some of which deviate from the findings reported here. These observations should not be interpreted as strength reduction due to porosity in the hardened FRCA mortar but rather as a consequence of altered w/c ratios.

A balanced approach involves using dry FRCA while moderately increasing mixing water, though not to the full extent of FRCA's absorption capacity, compared to the reference mortar. Additionally, incorporating superplasticizers proves effective in mitigating strength loss at higher FRCA substitution levels.

Fig. 12 Variation of flexural strength according to the replacement rate of FRCA (w/c = 0.6).

Fig. 13 Variation of flexural strength according to the replacement rate of FRCA (w/c = 0.5).

Fig. 14 Variation of flexural strength according to the replacement rate of FRCA (w/c = 0.4).

Fig. 15 shows the relationship between the compressive strength and the flexural strength derived from the testing data. Additionally, it displays the relationship derived from the (Eurocode 2, 2005) equation, which is as follows:

$$R_t = 0.3 R_c^{2/3} \quad (5)$$

Where the compressive strength is denoted by R_c and the direct tensile strength by R_t . Equation (5) is divided by 0.6 since three-point bending is used to measure the tensile strength. Based on the experimental findings, the following empirical expression was produced:

$$R_t = 0.147 R_c^{1.0749} \quad (6)$$

The Eurocode 2 Equation for flexural strength at different ages is not able to predict the actual flexural strength values of the concrete employed in this investigation with high accuracy, as Fig. 15 illustrates. Flexural strength also varies proportionately with compressive strength.

Fig. 15 Compressive strength and tensile strength correlation

3.6 Total shrinkage

In the case of recycled mortars, shrinkage problems are even more to be feared, given the high absorption of FRCA when used in the dry state. The results illustrated in Fig. 16 group together the values reached after 140 days of exposure. For low w/c ratios (w/c=0.5 and w/c = 0.4), the presence of recycled aggregates has little effect on the final shrinkage value. On the other hand, the shrinkage of mortars with recycled aggregates is greater with high w/c ratios (w/c=0.6) and in a manner proportional to the substitution rate.

It is obvious that recycled aggregates play a fundamental role in the kinetics and ultimate value of total shrinkage. The significant porosity promotes desiccation and allows water to escape from the interstices of the dough while the irregular shape of the grains hinders deformability and slows down this deformation. This combination of opposing effects gives a non-monotonic evolution to shrinkage which remains closely linked to the w/c ratio. Also this may be linked to the faster development of compressive strength in recycled mortars as also documented by other authors (Bogas et al., 2022).

From Fig. 16, we generally notice that the shrinkage in the open air of recycled mortars is significantly greater than that of SN mortar, especially for high w/c ratios, and show that the shrinkage of FRCA based mortar from old crushed concrete for a w/c of 0.6, 0.5 and 0.6 is higher by 52%, 21% and 20% respectively than that of the control at 140 days. Drying shrinkage increases with the rate of replacement of ordinary aggregates with recycled aggregates. Withdrawal increases significantly for a replacement rate above 25%. This finding is in line with that of (Carriço et al., 2022), who explained that the high shrinkage of the mortars based on FRCA is most likely caused by the recycled aggregates' high porosity and the mortar's considerable water absorption from the old concrete that covers them. Furthermore, with time, the old

mortar that is affixed to the recovered aggregates keeps getting smaller (Guo & Wang, 2012).

Fig. 16 Variation of the total shrinkage at 140 days according to the w/c ratio.

3.7 Capillary absorption

The results of capillary absorption (Sorptivity) are presented in Fig. 17 for the different mortar mixtures. Different trends were identified for the three water/cement ratios tested. At the low w/c ratio, all mixtures containing recycled aggregates showed higher absorption values compared to the reference mixture. At a replacement of 100% and a measurement time of 24 hours the absorption coefficients values mark higher sorptivity values of 61% and 46% for the w/c ratios of 0.5 and 0.6 respectively compared to the control mortar, and at a replacement of 50% and a measurement time of 24 hours the absorption coefficients values mark higher sorptivity values of 29% compared to the control mortar.

The composition and fines content of recycled aggregates, as well as the variations in the porous structure of recycled aggregates and new cement paste, which are likely impacted by the presence of old pastes, appear to be some of the factors that affect the capillary absorption process (Katz & Kulisch, 2017).

According to the results found by (Katz & Kulisch, 2017), these parameters can influence the connectivity and tortuosity of the pores of new mortars, thus leading to a large variation in the results. The use of the highly porous aggregate, with a replacement rate of 100% and a low w/c ratio, led to significant differences between the aggregates and the new paste, which, combined with low fine particle content, led to very high absorption values. At the higher water/water ratio, the difference between the pore structure of the recycled aggregate and that of the new paste is smaller and therefore the absorption values are lower for this aggregate.

Fig. 17 Measured capillarity coefficients of the different mortars tested.

Fig. 18 demonstrates a relationship between the capillarity coefficients and the total shrinkage got from the experimental results, the relationship can be expressed by the following equation:

$$C_a = 21.677 T^{2.4237} \quad (7)$$

Where C_a , is the capillarity coefficients and T is the total shrinkage. The relationship is compelling and the correlation coefficients are very close to the unit, it takes value of 0.9618. Fig. 18 show that the capillarity coefficients vary proportionally with the total shrinkage accurately the actual flexural strength values of the concrete used in this study.

Fig. 18 Analysis of the relationship between capillarity coefficients and total shrinkage of mortars with different mixtures

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

This study investigated the characteristics of fresh and hardened mortar incorporating recycled aggregates, leading to the following key findings:

Fine recycled concrete sand exhibits significantly greater water absorption compared to natural sand. This behavior is attributed to the high porosity of the residual cement paste, which directly affects both the fresh and hardened properties of recycled sand-based mortars.

By increasing the substitution rate of FRCA in mortar mixtures a clear increase in mechanicals

resistances was observed, this increase is perhaps attributed to the great absorption of FRCA which influences the effective w/c ratio

Mortars incorporating recycled aggregates typically exhibit substantially higher air-drying shrinkage compared to natural sand (NS) mortars, particularly at elevated water-to-cement ratios.

When compared to the reference mix, every recycled aggregate combination demonstrated increased capillary water absorption, as evidenced by higher sorptivity measurements

This study proposes mathematical models to predict compressive strength and rheological properties based on mortar composition parameters, including FRCA substitution rate, superplasticizer content, and water-cement ratio. The high correlation coefficients (approaching unity) demonstrate the models' strong predictive validity.

A comprehensive understanding of recycled material properties is essential to effectively manage their influence on concrete and mortar performance. Given the inherent variability of demolition waste which poses significant control challenges the development of enhanced quality assurance protocols becomes imperative. In particular, improving the accuracy of residual mortar content measurements could serve as a key quality control parameter for recycled aggregates.

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